

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

D9.4 Validation and recommendations for lawmakers and policymakers

Deliverable information	
WP number and title	WP9 Legal and Ethical Framework
Lead beneficiary	KU Leuven Centre for IT & IP Law (KUL-CTP)
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	31 December 2024
Actual date of delivery	30 November 2024
Author	KU Leuven Center for IT & IP Law (KUL-CTP)
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (KUL-CTP). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
0.1	15/09/2024	Table of Contents (ToC)	Elisabetta Biasin (KUL-CTP)	Input ToC
0.2	14/10/2024	Feedback to the ToC	ISW WP9 Partners	Oral discussion over the ToC via <i>ad hoc</i> WP9 meeting and written feedback
0.3	21/11/2024	First draft	Elisabetta Biasin (KUL-CTP)	Submission for internal review and partners' feedback
0.4	28/11/2024	Internal Review	Ana Maria Correa Harcus	Internal review
0.5	28/11/2024	UNIBO Feedback & Partners' Review	Prof. dr. Marco Viceconti (UniBO)	Feedback and Partner's Review
0.6	29/11/2024	Feedback Implementation	Elisabetta Biasin (KUL-CTP)	Feedback implementation to Final Version
1.0	30/11/2024	Final Version	UNIBO	Submission to the EC Portal

THIS DOCUMENT HAS NOT BEEN FORMALLY APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION YET AND, THEREFORE, IT MAY BE SUBJECT TO CHANGES.

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable, ‘**D9.4—Validation and recommendations for lawmakers and policymakers**’, is part of Work Package 9, ‘Ethical and Legal Framework’ (WP9) of the In Silico World (ISW) project. This report is based on previous research carried out throughout the ISW project, including ‘D9.1—Legal and Ethical Inventory’, ‘D9.2—In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements’, and D9.3, ‘Implementation guidance and guidelines’.

The first and second deliverables assessed the core legislation and ethical principles relevant to In Silico Trials. The third deliverable provided guidelines on the ethical and legal aspects of In Silico Trials for researchers and end users. This fourth deliverable offers **legal recommendations for the European Union’s (EU) legislature, regulators and policymakers**. It builds on the previously identified areas of investigation, i.e. data governance and privacy, medical devices and medicinal products, and artificial intelligence, and, in light of the project experience, offers policy recommendations. These recommendations, further detailed throughout the report, are recapitulated as follows:

Recommendations to the EU legislature, regulators and policymakers

Data Governance and Privacy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Provide data protection guidance on the use of synthetic data</i> 2. <i>Support in silico and health stakeholders complying with forthcoming EHDS opt-out requirements</i>
Medical Devices and Medicinal Products	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. <i>Clarify the regulatory pathways for modelling and simulation and In Silico Trials for medical devices</i> 4. <i>Incorporate In Silico Trials in the binding text of the EU pharmaceutical reform</i>
Artificial Intelligence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. <i>Ensure the smooth interaction between the AI Act and medical laws</i>

This report follows a **recommendatory** method. It represents the third and last step of the research conducted within ISW WP9, which is dedicated to analysing the ethical and legal framework for In Silico Trials. The present report, grounded on the analysis carried out in D9.1, D9.2, and D9.3, is the final report of ISW WP9. It **concludes the legal and ethical research of the In Silico World project**.

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

This deliverable is based on the former deliverables ‘D9.1 – Ethical and legal inventory of in silico trials’¹, ‘D9.2 – In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements’², and ‘D9.3 – Implementation guidance and guidelines’³ – which identified and described the relevant **legal and ethical framework** for In Silico Trials.⁴ Considering the former works, this report offers **recommendations** to the European Union’s (EU) legislature, regulators, and policymakers as part of the conclusive steps of the In Silico World project.

1.2. Document outline

This document reports on the **legal domains** studied throughout the In Silico World project: 1) Data Governance and Privacy (section 2), 2) Medical Devices and Medicinal Products (section 3), and 3) Artificial Intelligence (section 4). Every section contains three sub-sections. The **legal challenges** (‘Legal challenges’) encountered by the ISW partners throughout the project for every identified legal domain. The identified legal challenges concern the following topics: anonymisation and the further processing of health data (section 2.2.1); the absence of references to “In Silico Trials” within EU legal texts on medical products (section 3.2.1); and the adaptation to the AI Act for *in silico* stakeholders (section 4.2.1).

After describing the legal challenges for every domain, the report offers **legal recommendations** to the EU legislature, regulators and policy-makers. For data governance, the report suggests that relevant data governance bodies provide guidance on data protection and the use of synthetic data (section 2.3.1), secondary use of data, and EHDS’s opt-out requirements (2.3.2). For medical products, the report advocates EU bodies to clarify the regulatory pathways for modelling and simulation for medical devices (3.2.1) and incorporate “In Silico Trials” in the binding texts of the forthcoming EU pharmaceutical reform (section 3.3.2). Finally, for the field of Artificial Intelligence, the report argues for the need for a smooth interaction between the AI Act and medical laws (section 4.4.1).

Every domain contains a third and final sub-section with forward-looking perspectives on the **open issues** for In Silico Trials and **future research perspectives**. A core open issue identified across domains in this report concerns the difficult interplay between laws, such as data (section 2.4.1), AI and medical laws (section 4.4.1). In terms of forthcoming research, further developments in medical products (section 3.4.2) and AI (section 4.4.1) will likely pave the way for new practical issues worth assessing from a legal studies perspective. Section 6 **concludes** the deliverable.

¹ Elisabetta Biasin, ‘In Silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory’ (Zenodo 2022) <<https://zenodo.org/record/7104079>> accessed 10 January 2023.

² Elisabetta Biasin, ‘In Silico World D9.2 In-Depth Analysis of Legal and Ethical Requirements’ (Zenodo 2023) <<https://zenodo.org/record/7991233>> accessed 31 May 2023.

³ Elisabetta Biasin and others, ‘In Silico World D9.3 Implementation Guidance and Guidelines’ ([object Object] 2024) <<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11173757>> accessed 14 May 2024.

⁴ *ibid.*

2. Data Governance and Privacy

2.1. Relevance to In Silico Trials

2.1.1. Overview

In Silico Trials entail **processing an individual's personal data**, including health data. These data are often processed in healthcare settings (such as hospitals) and further processed by the same or other entities for research purposes (a practice that can also be referred to as “secondary use”).⁵ The relevant **privacy, data protection and governance framework** was outlined in D9.1 and D9.2. The data legal framework includes transnational sources and instruments, such as the Council of Europe's Convention 108⁶, EU primary law, such as the European Treaties⁷, and data protection-specific laws, such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁸.

Data governance pieces of legislation, such as the Data Act⁹ and the Data Governance Act¹⁰, are also relevant. These laws introduced new fundamental concepts for health research – such as “data altruism” – and established new entities – such as “data intermediaries” – within the complex dynamics of health data processing. The former reports also highlighted the relevance of the forthcoming **European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation**¹¹. Once approved, this latter Regulation will entail several changes, including new health data governance and sharing requirements. It will introduce new mechanisms for the primary and secondary use of electronic health data, establish new entities and bodies for data governance, and create new “secure processing environments” for these to be shared among the different actors.¹²

⁵ In addition to health data, several researchers of In Silico Trials use artificially generated data that mimics the properties of “real” health data, i.e., synthetic data.

⁶ Council of Europe, Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, ETS No. 108, 28.01.1981 (1981); Council of Europe, Protocol amending the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (2018).

⁷ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union [2008] OJ C115/13 (TEU); Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [2007] OJ C 115/47 (TFEU).

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L119/1 (GDPR).

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) [2023] OJ L2023/2854.

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) [2022] OJ L152/1.

¹¹ At the time of writing this report, the EHDS Regulation is not yet formally published in the EU Official Journal. This report considers the latest available version, i.e. the EHDS provisional agreement as negotiated by the relevant EU parties in the first semester of 2024, i.e. Council of the European Union, Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space - Analysis of the final compromise text with a view to agreement (2022/0140(COD)), 18 March 2024 (hereinafter EHDS proposal, compromise text).

¹² For an in-dept analysis of the innovations brought by the EHDS Regulation, see former reports Biasin (n 1); Biasin, Elisabetta (n 2).

2.2. Legal challenges

2.2.1. Further processing of health data

The ISW project partners encountered several legal challenges related to data protection, governance, and privacy. The most relevant one relates to the rules concerning health data processing for scientific research in healthcare settings. As explained in D9.1, **data sharing** across healthcare facilities and researchers helps develop, testing, and validate *in silico* models. The GDPR is currently the core law for the primary and secondary use of health data in the context of research¹³. Article 9 of the GDPR establishes that Member States may introduce further conditions, including limitations, concerning the processing of genetic data, biometric data, or health data. Therefore, EU Member States' national laws may add further requirements and specifications for the **further processing of personal electronic health data**.

Throughout the years of implementation of EU data protection laws, EU Member States have diverged in setting additional requirements.

(Example: Italy). One notable example is the Italian case. Until May 2024, the further processing of data concerning health for medical, biomedical, and epidemiological research required the prior authorisation of the data protection supervisory authority.¹⁴ The Italian “Privacy Code”, in its previous formulation, required the prior consultation of the Italian supervisory authority (“Garante”). After public debates, a new law was adopted and prior authorisation is no longer required in Italy.¹⁵ However, throughout the years, healthcare research stakeholders based in Italy have had to consider this requirement before starting a new research project. The new formulation of Article 110 of the Privacy Code is now dedicated to obtaining the prior authorisation of the ethical committees – more in alignment with the ongoing practices in the European Union.

The case above shows how the GDPR (Article 9 notably) may have allowed **divergences in its implementation** for processing health data across countries.¹⁶ During the project Consortium meetings, *in silico* stakeholders expressed their concern that, while presented as a tool for harmonising Member States’ legislation on data protection, GDPR (and Article 9 thereof) was “hiding” a large margin of manoeuvre between Member States.¹⁷ It is difficult to envisage a new formulation of the GDPR (or other health data laws) going beyond this problem. This fragmentation issue is connected to the so-called EU “principle of subsidiarity”, which leaves it to the Member States to self-determine their appropriate ethical and legal standards for scientific research. Moreover, health matters are within shared competencies according to EU Treaties. Nevertheless, it is worth

¹³ “Secondary use” and “further processing of health data” have a similar yet distinct meaning. “Further processing of personal data” is based on the relevant provisions of the GDPR and concerns the further processing of *personal* data – in the In Silico Trials context, of personal health data. “Secondary use” of health data is based on the relevant definitions of the EHDS proposal. Therefore, the “further processing” refers to personal data, while the second refers to the broader category of electronic health data, which encompasses, in the EHDS proposal, both personal and non-personal data. See EHDS proposal, compromise text, art 2(2)(e).

¹⁴ See former article 110 of the Decreto legislativo 30 giugno 2003, n.196 recante il “Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali”. The article (article 110 of the Privacy Code) was modified in the spring of 2024.

¹⁵ Decreto legge 2 marzo 2024, n. 19, convertito, con modificazioni, dalla L. 29 aprile 2024, n. 56, art. 44, comma 1-bis,

¹⁶ An EU-wide study carried out a comprehensive assessment of national rules and their variations across the EU Member States. See Johan Hansen and others, *Assessment of the EU Member States’ Rules on Health Data in the Light of GDPR. Assessment for the European Commission’s Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency* (Publications Office 2021) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2818/546193>> accessed 16 October 2024.

¹⁷ In-depth analyses of the mentioned problem usually consider the relevance of Member States’ competences in health matters. This kind of situation is not because of the GDPR’s formulation. It is a matter of EU primacy and it is the consequence of the so-called shared competencies between the European Union and the Member States in health matters.

mentioning that the Consortium researchers envisaged this as a challenge connected to an existing legal requirement. Such a requirement has implied variations in national laws, resulting in more administrative burdens and **issues in planning and executing research** in certain Member States.

2.2.1. Anonymisation and the use of synthetic data

Silico Trials may entail the extensive use of **synthetic data**. They can be used at the beginning of the research process to train *in silico* models and at later stages to train for verification and validation. As anticipated in D9.2, synthetic data are artificially generated data aimed at reproducing the characteristics of a given dataset. The literature usually distinguishes between fully synthetic, partial, and hybrid synthetic data.¹⁸ Synthetic data are used in healthcare and several other sectors, such as autonomous driving, finance, and insurance.¹⁹

Synthetic data undoubtedly affect privacy. The DGA considers them ‘privacy-preserving methods that could contribute to a more privacy-friendly processing of data’.²⁰ However, there are legal challenges related to their use. The most important one relies on the **interpretative uncertainty about their qualification as personal data**. Some academic contributions and grey literature have already commented on the topic.²¹ The discussions are based on different arguments and positions. Some healthcare stakeholders believe that synthetic data is always anonymised.²² Others believe that it is not such a straightforward element and that it depends on a case-by-case basis.²³ In practice, there are also less legally aware approaches dismissing such data protection aspects. Moreover, often anonymisation is confused with pseudonymisation, entailing rather problematic consequences.²⁴

As outlined in D9.2, there exist, in fact, two primary “schools of thought” on anonymisation (often referred to in the literature as the *objective* and *relative* criteria)²⁵. The more flexible approach is the “relative” criterion, which suggests considering data as personal on a case-by-case basis. In contrast, the objective criterion is, in principle, stricter and tend to consider data as personal when any third party could identify

¹⁸ H Surendra and HS Mohan, ‘A Review of Synthetic Data Generation Methods For Privacy Preserving Data Publishing’ (2017) 6 International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research.

¹⁹ See eg, James Jordon and others, ‘Synthetic Data -- What, Why and How?’ (arXiv, 2022) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.03257>> accessed 6 November 2024; Zhihang Song and others, ‘Synthetic Datasets for Autonomous Driving: A Survey’ (2024) 9 IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles 1847; Samuel A Assefa and others, ‘Generating Synthetic Data in Finance: Opportunities, Challenges and Pitfalls’, *Proceedings of the First ACM International Conference on AI in Finance* (ACM 2020) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3383455.3422554>> accessed 6 November 2024.

²⁰ DGA, rec 7.

²¹ See eg Puja Myles, Johan Ordish and Richard Branson, ‘Synthetic Data and the Innovation, Assessment, and Regulation of AI Medical Devices’ <https://cprd.com/sites/default/files/2022-02/Synthetic%20data_RA%20proof.pdf>.

²² See, for example, the references in Lorenzo Cristofaro, ‘Legal Status of Synthetic Data | LinkedIn’ (18 October 2023) <<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/legal-status-synthetic-data-lorenzo-cristofaro/>> accessed 17 September 2024.

²³ Fontanillo López César Augusto and Elbi Abdullah, ‘On the Legal Nature of Synthetic Data’, *NeurIPS 2022 Workshop on Synthetic Data for Empowering ML Research* (2022) <<https://openreview.net/pdf?id=MOKMbGL2yr>>.

²⁴ If synthetic data are considered anonymous in a given context, although they are still linkable to identified individuals, data protection is no longer respected, and patients could be at risk of reidentification.

²⁵ See also César Augusto Fontanillo López and Abdullah Elbi, ‘On Synthetic Data: A Brief Introduction for Data Protection Law Dummies’ (2022).

them.²⁶ While academic researchers and practitioners have started focusing on the topic, **no EU guidance is fully dedicated to legal interpreting synthetic data from a data protection perspective.**

Consequently, healthcare researchers usually refer to their internal compliance officers/DPOs, which often have **different orientations** as to whether synthetic data could be considered anonymous or pseudonymous. Such a situation can be seen as a **legal challenge**, both for scientific researchers — who face uncertainty in their research project planning and execution — and for health institutions — who bear the risk of not complying with the GDPR when incorrectly interpreting data protection legal requirements.

2.3. Recommendations

2.3.1. Provide data protection guidance on the use of synthetic data

Stakeholders using synthetic data are lost in the interpretative maze of understanding which legal requirements apply to **synthetic data**. Leaving healthcare stakeholders to decide for themselves whether synthetic data are anonymous or pseudonymous risks them being fined on the one hand, and on the other hand, it may pose patients with heightened risks (for example, they can suffer risks of undue exposure if healthcare stakeholders hold that synthetic datasets are fully anonymised while in reality, they can still be linked to the original datasets and the individuals).

There is no EU-wide guidance for healthcare stakeholders suggesting the most appropriate **data protection** technical and organisational measures for processing synthetic data. Currently, however, stakeholders can only rely on guidance tailored to anonymisation techniques.²⁷ However, ad hoc guidance on synthetic data could mitigate the legal uncertainty for healthcare researchers and patients.

This report, therefore, recommends the adoption of guidance addressed to healthcare stakeholders describing the most important aspects of processing synthetic data while conducting healthcare research (including, but not limited to — for example — anonymisation, pseudonymisation, data sharing aspects, and consent).

<p>Recommendation: Provide data protection guidance on the use of synthetic data</p>
<p><i>In silico stakeholders lack appropriate data protection guidance for processing synthetic data. The European Union institutions or any EU or data protection-relevant entities (such as the EDPB) should consider providing guidance documentation on the data protection aspects for synthetic data.</i></p>

2.3.2. Support in silico and healthcare stakeholders complying with forthcoming opt-out requirements

As observed in D9.2 and D9.3, the **forthcoming EHDS Regulation** will likely change the legal framework on health data sharing in the European Union. It will introduce new rules for health data sharing, new patient rights, primary and secondary use of electronic health data, and data sharing practices.

As part of the new rules on patients' rights, the EHDS Regulation will allow patients to oppose the further processing of their electronic health data (opt-out). The European Commission's proposal for the EHDS Regulation initially did not foresee an **opt-out** requirement. However, after many stakeholders' interactions with lawmakers, the March 2024 EHDS compromise text included provisions on the matter. On that occasion,

²⁶ Furthermore, patients could be exposed to possible risks to their fundamental rights to health or non-discrimination. Further to these criteria, the European Court of Justice (ECJ) case law plays a fundamental role in shaping the orientations on anonymisation. See eg Case C-582/14 Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland [2016].

²⁷ Article 29 Working Party, 'Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques' <https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp216_en.pdf>.

the text was amended to include provisions for patients to ‘effectively opt-out of the primary and secondary processing of electronic health data’.²⁸

The possibility of providing patients with the option of **opting out** of the primary or secondary use of their data is not a new right in health law. In the past, other examples were implemented in different legal systems, such as the United Kingdom (UK)²⁹ or Australia³⁰. The EHDS Regulation will allow Member States to decide whether to introduce the right to opt- out of the **primary use** of electronic health data.³¹ The opt-out will concern accessing electronic health data from the Electronic Health Records (EHRs). It will be a voluntary mechanism for the Member States, as they will be called to establish the rules and specific safeguards regarding the objection mechanisms.

The EHDS Regulation will foresee the possibility of patients opting out of the **secondary use** of their electronic health data. Similarly to the primary use, Member States will be called to provide for ‘accessible and easily understandable’ opt-out mechanisms for secondary use.³² Opt-out will not be an absolute right. The EHDS Regulation will allow Member States to foresee ‘justified exceptions’ that must be proportionate and respect the essence of fundamental rights.³³ Scientific research ‘done for important reasons of public interest by public sector bodies’ could be a **justified exception**. Health data access bodies will be called to assess the justification of such exceptions.³⁴ Health data users will have to justify using the override for an individual access application or data request.

The recitals of the EHDS Regulation suggest that **scientific research for important reasons of public interest** could, for example, include ‘research addressing unmet medical needs, including for rare diseases, or emerging health threats’.³⁵ Nevertheless, from the perspective of *in silico* stakeholders, it will be necessary to

²⁸ See EHDS Regulation, march 2024 compromise text, rec 37c, ‘To balance the need of data users to have exhaustive and representative datasets with the autonomy of natural persons over their personal electronic health data that are considered particularly sensitive, natural persons should have a say in the processing of their personal electronic health data for secondary use under this Regulation, in the form of a right to opt-out from having such their personal electronic health data being made available for secondary use. An easily understandable and accessible user-friendly opt-out mechanism should be provided for in this regard. Moreover, it is imperative to provide natural persons with sufficient and complete information regarding their right to opt-out, including on the benefits and drawbacks when exercising this right’.

²⁹ In the UK, the right to opt-out has been set since 2013 (with the care.data programme) and, thereafter, with the National Data Opt-Out system. For further sources on the history of UK’s opt-out, see Paola Aurucci, *Il Trattamento Dei Dati Personali Nella Ricerca Biomedica. Problematiche Etico-Giuridiche* (Edizioni Scientifiche Italiane - Università degli Studi di Torino 2023); Janos Meszaros, Chih-hsing Ho and Marcelo Corrales Compagnucci, ‘Nudging Consent and the New Opt-Out System to the Processing of Health Data in England’ in Marcelo Corrales Compagnucci and others (eds), *Legal Tech and the New Sharing Economy* (Springer Singapore 2020) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-15-1350-3_5> accessed 28 August 2024; Pam Carter, Graeme T Laurie and Mary Dixon-Woods, ‘The Social Licence for Research: Why *Care.Data* Ran into Trouble’ (2015) 41 *Journal of Medical Ethics* 404.

³⁰ Chris McCall, ‘Opt-out Digital Health Records Cause Debate in Australia’ (2018) 392 *The Lancet* 372.

³¹ EHDS Regulation, March 2024 compromise text, art 8h.

³² *ibid*, art 35e(2)(1).

³³ See EHDS Regulation, March 2024 compromise text, section II of the explanatory text: ‘A right to opt-out is introduced in all Member States. However, Member States may provide under national law, for mechanisms to implement justified exceptions for the purposes referred to in Article 34(1) points (a)-(c) and for scientific research done for important reasons of public interest by public sector bodies, including a third party acting on behalf of or commissioned by such entities. These exceptions shall respect the essence of the fundamental rights and need to be proportionate. The assessment of the justifications will be done by the health data access body and the Member States should notify the Commission of adopted national law on the opt-out mechanism’.

³⁴ EHDS Regulation, March 2024 compromise text, rec 37c.

³⁵ EHDS Regulation, March 2024 compromise text, rec 37c.

understand more specifically whether their research can be framed as a ‘justified exception’ for the purposes of opt-out mechanisms.³⁶ In the event that *in silico* stakeholders figure as data users for secondary use of data, they will also need to understand how they will have to justify their data use with regard to the ‘respect of the essence of fundamental rights’.

Finally, neither primary nor secondary use provisions are specific enough to materially guide health stakeholders in setting up the appropriate **mechanisms for facilitating opting out**. Further directions, therefore, by the European Commission and/or the relevant national and EU bodies will be needed to correctly implement the EHDS Regulation’s opt-out legal requirements.

Recommendation: Support in silico and healthcare stakeholders complying with the forthcoming EHDS opt-out requirements

The forthcoming EHDS Regulation will establish new requirements for the further processing of health data in the context of health research (i.e., ‘secondary use’). However, some of the EHDS Regulation’s opt-out requirements may be too general and might entail legal uncertainty for in silico stakeholders. Detailed guidance will be needed to help in silico stakeholders assess their case and the concrete mechanisms to allow patients to opt out of primary and secondary use of electronic health data.

2.4. Issues and questions for future research

2.4.1. Interplay between data laws

The introduction of new pieces of data law, such as the DGA and the EHDS Regulation, has added complexity to the existing legal framework. During the project, the ISW partners highlighted possible constraints or difficulties stemming from the forthcoming pieces of legislation. The issue is mirrored to some extent in academic discussions on health data governance, as many refer to the **inconsistencies** on the one hand or **overlapping between the EHDS, DGA and the GDPR** on the other hand. These inconsistencies include the difficulty in matching the legal basis for the further processing of health data between the EHDS and the GDPR and the rules on data altruism and consent between the DGA and the GDPR.³⁷

The interplay of data laws is also a field that will require further exploration in the future. Over the last two years, research has addressed and identified these problems (among the many: data portability and patients’ rights³⁸, competition aspects, feasibility and implementation, digital divide and ageing individuals³⁹). Data laws have been just approved, and therefore, many research strands analysing their interplay are just at their beginning. Further research will be needed to examine the final text and its interplay with other pieces of legislation.

³⁶ If those opt-out mechanism and exceptions will be regulated by the Member States.

³⁷ See eg Santa Slokenberga, ‘Scientific Research Regime 2.0? Transformations of the Research Regime and the Protection of the Data Subject That the Proposed EHDS Regulation Promises to Bring Along’ [2022] Technology and Regulation 135.

³⁸ Wenkai Li and Paul Quinn, ‘The European Health Data Space: An Expanded Right to Data Portability?’ (SSRN 2023) preprint <<https://www.ssrn.com/abstract=4516769>> accessed 8 September 2023; Teodora Lalova-Spinks and Daniela Brešić, ‘The Broadening of the Right to Data Portability for Internet-of-Things Products in the Data Act: Who Does the Act Actually Empower? (Part I)’ (16 June 2022) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/the-broadening-of-the-right-to-data-portability-for-internet-of-things-products-in-the-data-act-part-i/>>.

³⁹ Robin van Kessel and others, ‘The European Health Data Space Fails to Bridge Digital Divides’ [2022] BMJ e071913.

2.4.2. Secondary use of health data and liability

Making available data for reuse also raises questions over **liability**. Throughout the Consortium meetings, a recurrent question for In Silico World partners was: “What happens if other parties use a dataset that is released open access and then use the latter to develop a faulty tool”? This question reflects what can be described as a perceived open issue in the *in silico* community. **Liability** is a very particular domain in the EU legal system. In principle, civil liability rules are provided at a national level by civil law legislation. They apply differently based on the specificities of the different member states’ legal systems. There are also rules concerning criminal liability, which are also provided by national legislation. Specific rules at the EU level apply when damage is caused by defective products – for example, a medical device (including software as a medical device). In that case, consumers can invoke the protection brought by EU product liability laws.⁴⁰

Data protection legislation also includes provisions connected to liability. For personal data, the GDPR (Article 82) foresees that any person who has suffered material or non-material damage due to an infringement of the GDPR should have the right to receive compensation from the controller or processor for the damage sustained.⁴¹ Controllers or processors shall be exempt from liability if they prove that they are in any way responsible for the event giving rise to the damage.⁴² In addition, the provisions of the forthcoming AI Liability Directive can become relevant in terms of non-contractual fault-based civil law claims in cases where damages are caused by an AI system.⁴³

From an academic research perspective, liability law literature is vast. Many contributions have already analysed the evolution of liability paradigms in healthcare from several standpoints (as a matter of exemplification: third-party notified bodies’ liability⁴⁴, healthcare AI liability, and doctors’ liability using and discarding AI/medical device software suggestions⁴⁵). However, forthcoming research could analyse the effects of new data legislation – especially about the possible **degrees of responsibility and liability in the new data-sharing chain of actors**. Research could question the liability and the role of data intermediaries, the potential responsibility of data users (e.g. applying enrichments to existing datasets) or health data access bodies with regard to their oversight responsibility on the secure processing environments.

⁴⁰ Directive 1999/34/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 1999 amending Council Directive 85/374/EEC on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning liability for defective products [1999] OJ 141/20.

⁴¹ GDPR, art 82(1).

⁴² GDPR, art 82(3).

⁴³ European Commission, ‘Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on adapting non-contractual civil liability rules to artificial intelligence (AI Liability Directive)’ COM/2022/496 final.

⁴⁴ Jan De Bruyne and Cedric Vanleenhove, ‘Liability in the Medical Sector: The “Breast-Taking” Consequences of the Poly Implant Prothese Case’ (2016) 24 *European Review of Private Law* 823.

⁴⁵ Bethany A Corbin, ‘When “Things” Go Wrong: Redefining Liability for the Internet of Medical Things’ (2019) 71 *South Carolina Law Review* 1; W Nicholson Price, Sara Gerke and I Glenn Cohen, ‘Potential Liability for Physicians Using Artificial Intelligence’ (2019) 322 *JAMA* 1765; Angelica Marotta, ‘When AI Is Wrong: Addressing Liability Challenges in Women’s Healthcare’ (2022) 62 *Journal of Computer Information Systems* 1310.

3. Medical Devices and Medicinal Products

3.1. Relevance to In Silico Trials

3.1.1. Overview

Medical products legislation is the underpinning legal framework for in silico trials. In Silico Trials could, for instance, simulate devices or drug effects on a single patient or a group thereof; therefore, the medical devices and medicinal products frameworks are relevant.⁴⁶ As studied in D9.1, the applicable legal framework in the European Union for **clinical trials and medicinal products** includes the Declarations of Helsinki and Taipei⁴⁷, the Clinical Trials Regulation⁴⁸, Regulation 726/2004 on authorisation procedures and establishing EMA and the Community Code for Medicinal Products for Human Use⁴⁹. These laws set out the relevant ethical and legal standards for performing clinical trials for medicinal products and the appropriate tasks and activities for the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the EU entity competent to assess the safety and efficacy of medicinal products in the EU. Further relevant for In Silico Trials is the Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Product (ATMP) Regulation⁵⁰, as some solutions can qualify as ATMPs.⁵¹

The relevant legal framework for **medical devices** includes the Medical Device Regulation (MDR)⁵² and the In Vitro Medical Device Regulation (IVDR).⁵³ For medical devices and medicinal products, regulatory bodies regularly produce guidelines and other regulatory documentation to guide stakeholders in applying legal

⁴⁶ For medicinal products, the In Silico World's 'BoneStrenght' can exemplify how a solution can help assess the efficacy of pharmacological treatments and prevention (in the solution's case, for osteoporosis and prevention of fragility fractures). For medical devices, see UISS-MS and UISS-TB solutions. More details on the project's solutions are described in Goran Stanic and Desiree Caccaro, 'In Silico World Solution Dossier: Detailed Collection of the Results Produced within the In Silico World Project' (Zenodo, 30 October 2024) <<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14011767>> accessed 4 November 2024. Beyond the project's solutions, further exemplifications on the relevance of In Silico Trials to medical devices can be found in Food & Drug Administration, 'Assessing the Credibility of Computational Modeling and Simulation in Medical Device Submissions' (2023) 5 <<https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>>.

⁴⁷ World Medical Association, 'Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects' (World Medical Association, 1964, as last amended on 9th July 2018); World Medical Association, 'Declaration of Taipei. Research on Health Databases, Big Data and Biobanks' (World Medical Association) <<https://www.wma.net/what-we-do/medical-ethics/declaration-of-taipei/#:~:text=The%20Declaration%20of%20Taipei%20tries,powerful%20tool%20for%20increasing%20knowledge.>>> accessed 22 March 2022.

⁴⁸ Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC [2014] OJ L58/1.

⁴⁹ Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 laying down Community procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human and veterinary use and establishing a European Medicines Agency [2004] OJ L 136/30.

⁵⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2007 on advanced therapy medicinal products and amending Directive 2001/83/EC and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 [2007] OJ L324/121 (ATMP Regulation).

⁵¹ For example, the ISW "OcDefects" solution. See Stanic and Caccaro (n 48) 14.

⁵² Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC [2017] OJ L117/1 (MDR).

⁵³ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU [2017] OJ L117/176 (IVDR).

requirements. At the EU level, the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) issues relevant guidance for medical devices, and the EMA issues guidance for medicinal products.

In addition to laws and regulations, ethics and ethical standards have an essential role in biomedical research. D9.1 and D9.2 also provided an overview of the relevant biomedical ethics principles for In Silico Trials based on the principlist approach by Beauchamp and Childress.⁵⁴ These include the principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice.⁵⁵

3.2. Legal challenges

3.2.1. No reference to “In Silico Trials” in EU legal texts

Amongst the barriers to the uptake in silico trials, In Silico World Consortium enlisted a lack of clear regulatory pathways in the EU. Throughout the project, the legal research found that not only is there a lack of clear regulatory pathways in the EU, but also a lack of consistent legal terminology within the legal framework. There is **no specific ad hoc reference** in the existing medical product legal frameworks for “In Silico Trials” and regulatory texts do not consistently refer to in In Silico Trials, either.⁵⁶

D9.2 provided an in-depth analysis of the provisions and references relevant to In Silico Trials within the legal and regulatory framework of medical devices and medicinal products. For medical devices, D9.2 and further analysis show that the MDR does not explicitly mention “In Silico Trials”. The close references to In Silico Trials are the terms “**modelling**” and “**simulation**”, which correspond to the requirements for pre-clinical testing, design and manufacture of medical devices.⁵⁷ For medicinal products, the most relevant terms in the analysed legal texts are contained in Regulation 726/2004. The legal text does not mention “In Silico Trials” or *in silico* methods. Instead, the central concepts are “**novel methodologies**” and “**novel tools**” for research and development,⁵⁸ of which *In silico* methods could be considered a sub-category thereof.

The legal texts do not refer to “In Silico Trials.” This can be explained by the fact that innovative terminology varies over time, and many EU regulations are shaped technologically agnostic to be flexible while existing technological advancements evolve.⁵⁹ The same environment of In Silico Trials has seen several conceptual variations — often in need of clarification⁶⁰ — such as “Digital Twins”, “Virtual Human Twins”, “Virtual Twins”, “Virtual Patients”, “Virtual Cohorts”, and so on. Notwithstanding these notes, the absence of an explicit reference to “In Silico Trials” is perceived as a legal challenge for *in silico* stakeholders and may

⁵⁴ Tom L Beauchamp and James F Childress, *Principles of Biomedical Ethics* / Tom L. Beauchamp, James F. Childress (4th ed, Oxford University Press 1994).

⁵⁵ Further details are provided in D9.1 and D9.2. D9.3 contains an illustration exemplifying the practical relevance of these principles to In Silico Trials. See D9.3, Figure 2 ‘Examples of biomedical ethics principles applied in the context of In Silico Trials’.

⁵⁶ This report considers as “regulatory texts” the documentation provided by regulatory bodies, such as MDCG guidance, EMA’s reflection papers, opinions, Q&As etc.

⁵⁷ See D9.2, 44 for an in-depth analysis.

⁵⁸ Regulation 726/2004, art 56(3), second part. As more broadly described in D9.2, the EMA foresees a voluntary scientific procedure to establish the regulatory acceptability for novel methodologies for developing medicinal products.

⁵⁹ The GDPR is an example of such a technological-agnostic aspect. Other examples are those on Network Neutrality. See Elisabetta Biasin and Alessandro Bruni, ‘2019, Network Neutrality in the EU - between Zero-Rating and the Emerging of 5G Technologies’, *Rethinking IT and IP Law – Celebrating 30 Years CiTiP* (Intersentia 2019).

⁶⁰ as it happened as well for In Silico Trials, for which ISW stakeholders provided clarification. A much needed clarificatory work was recently published by the ISW project. See Janaki Raman Rangarajan and others, ‘In Silico World D5.6 - Information Package and Lecturing Materials’ (Zenodo 2024) <<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14044934>> accessed 16 November 2024.

contribute to the existing regulatory barriers for ISTs; thus, it is worth reporting for the purposes of this legal deliverable.

3.3. Recommendations

3.3.1. Clarify the regulatory pathways for modelling and simulation and In Silico Trials for medical devices

As D9.2 writes, the EU MDR and IVDR do not prohibit the use of evidence generated through computer modelling and simulation for medical devices. However, the implementation has not reached a maturity level, leaving **legal uncertainty** regarding the execution of in silico trials on medical devices.⁶¹ In fact, within the EU, the use of modelling and simulation in the certification process is currently limited to refining or reducing in vitro preclinical experiments. No qualification for new methodologies exists for medical devices, which implies that companies are called to produce evidence of models' credibility as part of new device submissions.⁶²

Modelling and simulation as references are also present in other legal frameworks, such as in the United States. In the mentioned system, the regulatory authority – the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) – established Modelling and Simulation Working Groups and issued relevant guidance for medical devices. While dedicated to “modelling and simulation” and “credibility assessment”⁶³, the latter guidance is also explicitly mentioning “in silico clinical trials”.⁶⁴ In the European Union, on the contrary, there is no EU-level specific document concerning either “modelling and simulation” or “In Silico Trials” specifically. Mentions are provided from time to time in guidance documentation (as explained above), but they are a side element rather than a central topic. The existing scientific and technological framework keeps evolving and *in silico* stakeholders might be in need of guidance to perform their activities in the most legally sound way possible. Therefore, this report recommends **the existing EU regulatory entities consider producing *ad hoc* guidance for evidence generation through *in silico* methods.**

<p>Recommendation: Clarify the regulatory pathways for modelling and simulation and In Silico Trials for medical devices</p>

<p><i>The medical device legal and regulatory frameworks mention modelling and simulation but make no ad hoc reference to In Silico Trials. The most relevant references include modelling and simulation, which nevertheless are limited to refinement or reduction of pre-clinical experiments. EU regulatory entities could consider issuing specific guidance addressing evidence generation through modelling and simulation and/or In Silico Trials.</i></p>
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3.3.2. Incorporate In Silico Trials in the binding text of the EU pharmaceutical reform

The former reports outlined the relevant legal framework for medicinal products and In Silico Trials, as also reported in the above section 3.1. After D9.2, an important development concerned the field of medicinal

⁶¹ See D9.2, 42. See also Francesco Pappalardo and others, ‘Toward A Regulatory Pathway for the Use of in Silico Trials in the CE Marking of Medical Devices’ (2022) 26 IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics 5282.

⁶² *ibid.*

⁶³ On this term, see below section 4.1.

⁶⁴ Food & Drug Administration (n 48) 6.

products: the Commission’s announcement of the pharmaceutical legislation revision happened in April 2023.⁶⁵ The proposed regulation mentions “in silico” within its text (emphasis added):

*“In particular, the marketing authorisation applicant and the marketing authorisation holder should take into account the principles laid down in Directive 2010/63/EU, including, where possible, use of new approach methodologies in place of animal testing. These can include but are not limited to: in vitro models, such as microphysiological systems including organ-on-chips, (2D and 3D) cell culture models, organoids and human stem cells-based models; in silico tools or read-across models”.*⁶⁶

Such mention within the proposed reform could be welcomed with favour by the *in silico* community. However, the **reference** to In Silico methods within the recitals of the legal text **does not make the provisions legally binding**. Recitals are a useful tool for interpreting the main body of an EU’s legal text. However, they do not have the same value as articles. Therefore, given the already existing references to *in silico* within the recitals of the pharmaceutical reform, this report suggests integrating the main body of the legal text with them to make them legally relevant.

Recommendation: Incorporate In Silico Trials in the binding text of the EU pharmaceutical reform

The EU is currently revising its pharmaceutical legal framework. The European Commission’s proposal refers to “in silico” in the recitals of the proposed regulation. To add starker, legally binding relevance to In Silico Trials, further references should be present in the articles of the legal text.

3.4. Issues and questions for future research

3.4.1. Model credibility

An open issue identified on different avenues by the In Silico World partners relates to the so-called “model credibility” and the absence of harmonised criteria for medical device *in silico* models. This can be seen as a **standardisation problem**, which consists of the lack of harmonised standards in the European Union for establishing the **credibility** of computational modelling in the field of medical devices.⁶⁷

The conversation on credibility has several disciplinary facets (including biomedical, engineering, regulatory science, etc.), and it becomes relevant from a legal perspective when it relates to the regulatory evaluation of medical products. For *in silico* stakeholders, having standardised methodologies for assessing the model’s credibility means having a common benchmark to understand the predictive capacity of an *in silico* model. Credibility allows for the demonstration that an *in silico* model is “trustworthy” within a given context of use. The In Silico World Consortium defined “credibility” in its SWOT analysis as ‘the highest possible predictive

⁶⁵ European Commission, ‘Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down Union procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing rules governing the European Medicines Agency, amending Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 and Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 726/2004, Regulation (EC) No 141/2000 and Regulation (EC) No 1901/2006’.

⁶⁶ *ibid*, rec 46.

⁶⁷ The most quoted resources available on model credibility is the ASME VV40:2018, a standard developed by the US-based “American Society of Mechanical Engineers” (ASME) standardisation body. ASME defines credibility as ‘the trust, established through the collection of evidence, in the predictive capability of a computational model for a context of use’. In the United States (US) – where the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) issued guidance on credibility assessment – the same definition is kept by the regulatory authority. See Food & Drug Administration (n 48).

error the model may commit compared to the value measured/observed in the experiment it aims to complement or supplement'.⁶⁸

In recent months, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standardisation body has established a new Work Programme (PWI 62-5) on “establishing the credibility of computational modelling.”⁶⁹ The target date is February 2026. The draft standard's contents are not available yet. It will be interesting to see how it evolves. If relevant to the medical device regulations, such a standard, for example, could be recognised as a harmonised standard and published in the European Union's Official Journal. In that event, *in silico* stakeholders could adhere to it and use it as a possible way to demonstrate compliance with specific safety requirements foreseen by the medical device regulations.

Finally, as also D9.2 pointed out both at the EU level and internationally, many **questions remain open** on credibility beyond the mere standardisation issue. In a recent report, the Avicenna Alliance posed the following questions: ‘How should models be verified and validated? Who will review and assess the simulation results, and which approval process will be followed? What standard requirements should medical device [manufacturers] meet when submitting CM&S data to support a market authorisation or when seeking reimbursement?’⁷⁰ Forthcoming research should also assess these issues from a legal perspective.

3.4.2. The future of medical products regulations

At the time of writing this report, several discussions are ongoing at the EU level on the regulations of medical devices and medicinal products.

During the second semester of 2024, the European Parliament discussed an **anticipated review of the medical device regulations**.⁷¹ Some Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) tabled a draft motion for resolution on the ‘urgent need to revise the Medical Devices Regulation’.⁷² The resolution—debated by the different parties—was echoed by statements of the European Commission during the European Parliament's session on 9 October 2024. On that occasion, the European Commission validated the need to proceed with an anticipated review of medical device regulations, especially with regard to the need to establish new regulatory pathways for “innovative devices”.

The final text of the **motion for the resolution** included several points **relevant to In Silico Trials**. Point 8 strongly called ‘to consider fast-track and prioritisation pathways for the approval of innovative technologies in areas of unmet medical needs and for devices linked to health emergencies’.⁷³ This could be relevant, for example, in cases where In Silico Trials can help with meeting the medical needs of underrepresented populations (e.g. pregnant patients or individuals with rare conditions). In the case of healthcare emergencies,

⁶⁸ ISW Consortium, SWOT analysis, 3.

⁶⁹ See IEC, ‘IEC TC 62 Dashboard > Projects: Work Programme, Up-to-Date Project Plan, Publications, Maintenance Cycle, Project Files, TC/SC in Figures’ (IEC) <https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:38:506279243064320::::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_APEX_PAGE,FSP_PROJECT_ID:1245,23,123752> accessed 2 November 2024. The publicly available description of the project states: ‘This project intends to prepare a new work item proposal for a standard that specifies requirements and recommendations for establishing the credibility of computational models used in the field of medical devices, including knowledge-based, data-based models, and hybrid models. The principles of verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification will be central elements of the new work item’.

⁷⁰ Avicenna Alliance, ‘Modelling and Simulation as a Transformative Tool for Medical Devices: The Transatlantic Regulatory Perspective’ (2018) 6.

⁷¹ European Parliament, ‘Resolution on the Urgent Need to Revise the Medical Devices Regulation’ 2024/2848(RSP) <[https://oeil.secure.europarl.europa.eu/oeil/popups/ficheprocedure.do?lang=en&reference=2024/2849\(RSP\)](https://oeil.secure.europarl.europa.eu/oeil/popups/ficheprocedure.do?lang=en&reference=2024/2849(RSP))>.

⁷² See European Parliament, ‘Agenda of Wednesday 9 October 2024’.

⁷³ European Parliament (n 73) point 8.

this point is also relevant, considering that Silico Trials can support and accelerate the assessment of an urgent medical product through an assessment of a virtual cohort of patients. The motion called on the Commission to formulate, by the end of Q1 of 2025, delegated and implemented acts of the MDR and IVDR and to propose, as soon as possible, a systematic revision of MDR/IVDR. It remains to be seen whether further actions will follow this political momentum.

From a broader perspective, given the motion for revision of medical device regulations and the current revision of the EU pharmaceutical law, it appears clear that the **EU legal framework for medical products will evolve**. Updated regulations and discussions⁷⁴ over the future of medical products regulation will pave the way for changes in healthcare policy across the EU. Future research in the legal domain will have to investigate the forthcoming legal requirements relevant to In Silico Trials and their most adequate regulatory pathways from a legal and ethical perspective.

4. Artificial Intelligence

4.1. Relevance to In Silico Trials

4.1.1. Overview

Throughout the project, the legal framework of Artificial Intelligence evolved significantly. Starting from the Commission’s Communication on Artificial Intelligence in 2018⁷⁵, the EU approved one of the first-in-kind AI legal texts worldwide: the AI Act.⁷⁶ As already outlined in D9.2, *in silico* tools may fall under the “AI system” definition provided by the AI Act. For example, a kind of medical device software simulating the effects of a given medicinal product could qualify as an AI system. Or, an AI-based tool that virtually simulates new compounds for medicinal products could qualify as an AI system. D9.2 analysed the main legal requirements of the AI Act – at that time, a legislative proposal – and suggested that in the majority of cases, *in silico* tools will not only fall under the definition of “AI systems” but also under the realm of “**high-risk AI systems**”.⁷⁷

The AI Act is currently the only AI-specific legal act of relevance for In Silico Trials in the EU. Further pieces of legislation may have an impact in the future, once approved – such as the proposed AI Liability Directive. Besides legally binding texts, relevant references are the AI HLEG Guidelines on Trustworthy AI and the ALTAI guidance documentation, which could be of help for *in silico* stakeholders conducting research on In Silico Trials.⁷⁸

⁷⁴ Several stakeholders have commented on the problems of medical products legislation, from different perspectives. For an In Silico Trials perspective see Viceconti Marco, ‘The Secret Life of Marco Viceconti: European Union: From the Land of Rights to the Land of Rules’ (*The Secret Life of Marco Viceconti*, 28 September 2024) <<https://secret-viceconti.blogspot.com/2024/09/european-union-from-land-of-rights-to.html>> accessed 8 November 2024. The piece sees EU overlapping laws and ‘the lack of a central authority’ for medical products as competitive problems for biomedical research and more broadly In Silico Trials innovation in the European Union.

⁷⁵ European Commission, ‘Communication from the Commission. Artificial Intelligence for Europe’ (2018).

⁷⁶ ‘MEPs Push Commission to Re-Open EU Medical Device Law Quickly’ (*euronews*, 12:21:17 +02:00) <<https://www.euronews.com/health/2024/10/10/meps-push-commission-to-re-open-eu-medical-device-law-quickly>> accessed 20 November 2024.

⁷⁷ For a detailed analysis of the AI Act’s scope and applicability to In Silico Trials, see D9.2, 46.

⁷⁸ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI’; High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Assessment List for Trustworthy AI’ (European Commission 2020) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>> accessed 28 August 2023.

4.2. Legal challenges

4.2.1. Interplay between AI and medical laws

The AI Act was approved on 1st August 2024 and will become directly applicable across the EU Member States. *In silico* stakeholders are preparing to adhere to the Regulation's forthcoming requirements. As part of their preparations, they are considering whether *in silico* tools may fall under the **definition of AI systems**. The EU AI Act categorises AI systems into different levels of risk — ranging from low to unacceptable. AI systems used in healthcare, including In Silico Trials, are likely to be classified as high-risk due to their potential impact on patient safety and well-being. Nevertheless, as also mentioned in the sections above, certain *in silico* tools may qualify not only as high-risk AI systems following the AI Act but also as **medical device software**.

Therefore, researchers and manufacturers must comply with both requirements foreseen by the AI Act (notably, Chapter III of the AI Act) such as risk management, data governance, technical documentation, transparency, human oversight, accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity. Nevertheless, some **requirements** are similar or **overlap** with existing requirements in other legislation, which may represent an important legal challenge for *In silico stakeholders*. For example, the MDR already has requirements on risk management, technical documentation or cybersecurity⁷⁹. *In silico* stakeholders and scientists will have to look specifically at the AI act, understand the most relevant requirements and assess, in light also of MDR requirements, how to implement them in the most appropriate way. Such regulatory complexity might constitute a legal challenge for *in silico* stakeholders.

4.3. Recommendations

4.3.1. Ensure the smooth interaction between the AI Act and medical laws

As discussed, a significant legal challenge arises from potential overlaps between the requirements of the AI Act and existing medical laws, such as the Medical Device Regulation (MDR). This raises the question: Which requirements will take precedence? Article 8 of the AI Act provides some general guidance for situations where a product incorporates an AI system that falls under both the AI Act and other EU harmonisation legislation, including the MDR:

“Where a product contains an AI system, to which the requirements of this Regulation as well as requirements of the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Section A of Annex I apply, providers shall be responsible for ensuring that their product is fully compliant with all applicable requirements under applicable Union harmonisation legislation. In ensuring the compliance of high-risk AI systems referred to in paragraph 1 with the requirements set out in this Section, and in order to ensure consistency, avoid duplication and minimise additional burdens, providers shall have a choice of integrating, as appropriate, the necessary testing and reporting processes, information and documentation they provide with regard to their product into documentation and procedures that already exist and are required under the Union harmonisation legislation listed in Section A of Annex I.” (Article 8 AI Act)

Despite this guidance, medical device software manufacturers are already facing challenges in understanding **how to harmonise the requirements** of the AI Act with those of the MDR. Studies suggest that achieving this integration is not straightforward, particularly given the nuanced obligations imposed by both frameworks.⁸⁰ EU policymakers should ensure that the AI Act provides clear guidelines for *in silico* AI-based systems. This

⁷⁹ For examples of requirement overlapping between the AI Act and MDR, see Elisabetta Biasin and Erik Kamenjašević, ‘Cybersecurity of Medical Devices: New Challenges Arising from the AI Act and NIS 2 Directive Proposals’ (2022) 3 International Cybersecurity Law Review 163.

⁸⁰ Francesca Gennari, ‘O Complementarity, Where Art Thou? Wading through the Medical Device Regulation and the AI Act Compliance: The case of Software as a Medical Device. A Primer’ [2024] BioLaw Journal - Rivista di BioDiritto 411.

clarity will be critical to fostering compliance while avoiding unnecessary duplication, inefficiencies, and regulatory burdens.

Recommendation: Ensure the smooth interaction between the AI Act and medical laws

In Silico Trials and in silico tools may fall under the scope of both AI law and medical laws, such as the MDR. As also some studies suggest, in the forthcoming months, it will be essential that the relevant bodies, such as the AI Office and/or the MDCG issue guiding documentation to navigate the different requirements.

4.4. Issues and questions for future research

4.4.1. Applications of the AI Act for In Silico Trials

As soon as the AI Act becomes enforceable, *in silico* stakeholders will have to consider compliance with its requirements and adherence throughout the AI system’s lifecycle. Issues and interpretative questions already exist (for example, the above-mentioned issue of AI Act/MDR interplay) and more are likely to grow in the forthcoming years.

One potential issue identified by In Silico World partners connected to AI-based In Silico Trials relates to the **availability and use of raw and synthetic data to train AI systems**. According to some *in silico* stakeholders, raw data have a relevant potential, for example, in helping to test or simulate a wider variety of scenarios to reduce the reliance on traditional methods like animal and human trials. Raw data could support synthetic data generation. Part of the issue will consist of ensuring that **transparency** mechanisms are in place to **document** how synthetic data are produced, validated and integrated into AI systems. There is, currently, little regulatory guidance on the availability, use and AI-based generation of data and synthetic data in general and in the context of In Silico Trials.⁸¹ Therefore, legal research will also be needed to foster regulatory activities in this respect.

In addition, some areas are likely to expand and will require further legal interpretative analysis. Possibly, **regulatory sandboxes** may be another one. Regulatory sandboxes are a possibility offered by the AI Act, allowing the testing and refinement of innovative AI-based technologies under regulatory supervision. Given that (AI-based) *in silico* tools are innovative AI systems, it might happen that *in silico* stakeholders will rely on them in the future to develop their solutions. Some research already started considering the potential applications of regulatory sandboxes in general and for healthcare.⁸² There is currently little research dedicated to regulatory sandboxes for In Silico Trials. Such a topic could be a promising research avenue for In Silico Trials' legal research.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable followed up the overview and in-depth analysis of the ethical and legal aspects studied in D9.1 and D9.2 for in Silico Trials and **concludes the research** conducted within WP9 of the In Silico World project (Ethical and Legal Framework). The analysis conducted throughout the research project has found a number of **legal challenges** for *in silico* stakeholders. As the report shows, these legal challenges, most of the time, are connected to the **difficult interplay** between current **legislation** and recently approved EU laws, such

⁸¹ Synthetic data, therefore, entail not only legal uncertainty in terms of data protection, but also in terms of regulatory science and evidence generation for medical products.

⁸² Thomas Buocz, Sebastian Pfothenhauer and Iris Eisenberger, ‘Regulatory Sandboxes in the AI Act: Reconciling Innovation and Safety?’ (2023) 15 Law, Innovation and Technology 357; Katerina Yordanova and Natalie Bertels, ‘Regulating AI: Challenges and the Way Forward Through Regulatory Sandboxes’ in Henrique Sousa Antunes and others (eds), *Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Artificial Intelligence and the Law*, vol 58 (Springer International Publishing 2024) <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-41264-6_23> accessed 14 May 2024.

as the EHDS Regulation and the AI Act. To help mitigate the identified challenges, the deliverable provided **recommendations** to EU legislature, regulators and policy-makers on the following areas of legislation: data governance and privacy, medicinal products and medical devices, and artificial intelligence. Finally, the report outlined the current practical **issues** with legal relevance that are deemed of particular importance for *in silico* stakeholders and contained suggestions for forthcoming *in silico* legal **research**. With this report, the ethical and legal research within the In Silico World project is concluded.

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